

Advancing Interdisciplinary Collaboration between Natural History and Cultural Heritage Collections

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Cultural Heritage samples archives share many commonalities with natural history collections – not only in their content (as many will contain natural history materials), but also in their function and importantly in the challenges that they face. This paper will present the work of the Heritage Samples Archives Initiative (HSAI) and its initiative to connect and collaborate with efforts in the Natural History archives community. HSAI was launched in September 2020 by ICCROM, an intergovernmental organization working in service to its 136 Member States to promote the conservation of all forms of cultural heritage, in every region of the world. In promoting the long-term survival and use of heritage samples archives, and the need to make these archives more accessible online, HSAI has started to explore the commonalities between Natural History archives and Cultural Heritage archives, and the opportunities that greater interdisciplinary collaboration and sharing offer for much needed practical, low-cost accessible solutions.

Many cultural heritage institutions around the world hold material samples archives comprising samples collected from heritage objects and sites, reference materials and replicas. These historic resources are non-renewable and have huge potential for future research and didactic purposes, but they are often little known, and their value under recognized. In addition, they pose very particular challenges concerning their physical safeguarding, access and use. As a result, they are critically threatened. Together with a partnership of over 25 institutions around the world, ICCROM is working to enhance the recognition and sustainable use of heritage samples archives, pursuing the following objectives:

- Raise awareness of the value and importance of heritage sample archives.
- Develop good practices, through improved policies, tools, and methodologies for sample archive management.
- Increase the accessibility and use of heritage samples archives, connecting them through open digital platforms.

